

The first time I worked with John was my very first public appearance in the United States.

As a coach, an accompanist, and a performer, he is a great musician with an impeccable artistry. But most of all, John has always been a dear and close friend.

Having introduced me to my first All-American audience, he holds a fond and indelible place in my heart.

Happy Birthday John!

"100 di quest'giorni"

Renata Scotto

December 2000

Parma